

A REVIEW: ROLE OF PHARMACIST IN PATIENT EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Clinical pharmacist play a major role in the patient counselling and also other activities that involves Adr monitoring, Drug interactions , patient medication adherence,DUE and many more that helps the patient for better care . patient counselling is a process in which the healthcare professional educate the patients about their medication and use of their medicines that are prescribed by the physician. The patient counselling is useful to all the patients but it plays a major role for Hypertensive patients , Diabetic patients and also pediatrics and geriatrics. Clinical pharmacist are engaged mainly for patient care they play a major role in patient medication adherence . By involving in patient counselling medications errors mainly prescription errors, dispensing errors can be eliminated. Clinical pharmacist for effective patient counseling need to follow some of the rules and regulations like that of communicate verbally,listen carefully , establish the trust.clinical pharmacist need to be very careful while counselling the patients like psychiatric, Geriatrics,and also pediatrics.and also interactions between patient and pharmacist should be clear and the pharmacist need to ask open ended questions rather than closed ended questions the pharmacist should always be concerned to the patient and should always available to the patient.

Key words: clinical pharmacist, patient counselling, medication errors,adr monitoring, drug interactions.

Introduction

Patient counselling refer to the guidance that is provided by the pharmacist to the patient about the use of right medicines. It involves the instructions to the patient about multiple aspects of medicines like contraindications, adverse drug effects, storage conditions and also route of administration patient counselling is one of the vital role of the pharmacist other than dispensing

and adr monitoring. Patient counselling is a process of providing information verbally or non verbally to the patient and also providing advice and assistance to help them about the use of medicines .This information is provided by the pharmacist to the patient directly or representatives of the patient about their well being and also patient illness and lift style modification the information to the patient can be provided by written material also[1]. Effective patient counseling involves the following points that to be considered they are mainly 1) improving the medication adherence 2) quality of life of patient will be provided 3) improving professional relationship between pharmacist and patient4) Understanding patient illness and the role of medication in their treatment 5) Reducing the incidence of unnecessary health care costs , medication errors and also common side effects [2].The pharmacist must have knowledge and also vital skills to provide accurate and also effective patient counseling and also patient education pharmacist must have the essential skills like opt to sharing the information to the patient and asking them open ended questions and also listening to them carefully without abruption patient education should be conducted by pharmacist in separate room or space that provides privacy to the patient . Patient counselling is very much important to the patient which is conducted by the clinical pharmacist for their better health[3].

OBJECTIVES OF PATIENT COUNSELLING:

The main objectives of patient counselling include namely,1) Interaction and consultation should be provided to the patient continuously 2) motivating the patient regarding the medication compliance or adherence 3) informing the patient prior about their disease management and also self care treatment

4) Making patient understand about their medication, side effects and also drug interactions [4].5) Drug interactions and adverse drug events must be prevented 6)The pharmacist should perceived as a professional status for offering pharmaceutical care 6) patient service should be enhanced 7) There should enough knowledge about drug information services 8) Identification of therapeutic drug monitoring and also narrow therapeutic index [5]

PURPOSE OF PATIENT COUNSELLING

There is a various purpose of patient counselling which include, assessing the patient and understanding the therapy of patient, enhancing patient compliance, and also includes use of

medication and adverse drug effects and also care of the patient is improved in many ways by patient counselling. Some of the ways of patient counselling that improve patient care involves

- 1) Reducing medication errors (prescription errors, transcription errors, dispensing errors, administration errors)
- 2) Reducing the drug drug interactions and also adverse drug effects
- 3) Increasing patient care [6]

CONTENTS OF PATIENT COUNSELLING.

The patient counselling involves the following contents that are

- 1) Name and all the details of the medication
- 2) Dosage form,dose and also route of administration
- 3) Techniques of monitoring therapy
- 4) correct storage of medication
- 5) alternative treatment if a dose is missed
- 6) Adverse drug effects,drug interactions and other contraindications should be monitored regularly
- 7) special precautions should be taken by the pharmacist with geriatric and pediatrics [7]

CLINICAL PHARMACIST

Clinical pharmacy has come in to the force in later 21st century as branch of pharmacy. It is the subject where the pharmacist are involved in multiple tasks like patient care, dispensing, patient counselling, pharmaceutical care and also monitoring of adr and also drug interactions. Clinical pharmacy allows professional skills and also optimizing patient safety .It not only allows the pharmacist to restrict for manufacturing services but also well being of a patient from all sides which mainly involves patient safety.And the person who is enrolled for Clinical pharmacy are called Clinical pharmacist . clinical pharmacy also involves the proper use of documentation of

the medication for the well being of patient and there safety[8]. Clinical pharmacist are generally involved to influence the prescribing of doctors as they have much knowledge about therapeutics and also they will be in regular contact with the prescriber's . Now a days mainly hospitals are following 2 strategies for influencing prescribers and also post graduate training of pharmacist that mainly improve the skills of therapeutics of the pharmacist and also improving the clinical practice[9].

ROLE OF CLINICAL PHARMACIST IN PATIENT COUNSELING

The main aim of

the Clinical pharmacist is to patient safety and provide appropriate mediation to the patient by ensuring that patient understands how to take medication there by preventing medication errors. The main role of clinical pharmacist is to make understand patient about their medication adherence with respect of dosage regimen and timing and dose. And also clinical pharmacist play a major role to the patient right from admission to the discharge about their medication and also checking their all routine needs. And mainly clinical pharmacist reduce the drug related problems by checking all the drugs and also taking DUE (Drug utilization review) and cross checking all the medication to prevent any unwanted effects [10].

The other roles mainly involves the following

Therapeutic drug monitoring and
narrow therapeutic index Patient
service

Collecting past medical history and improving
patient medical adherence Drug information
service

Pharmaceutical care

Prescription, dispensing and maximizing drug efficacy and
minimising drug toxicity Adverse drug events monitoring
and also checking drug interactions [11].

FEATURES OF EFFECTIVE PATIENT COUNSELLING BY CLINICAL PHARMACIST

For an effective patient counseling the clinical pharmacist must undergo the following they are mainly;

1) LISTEN

While treating patients about their medication, listening to the patient concern

And helping the needs of the patient is mandatory, there are 4 categories of listening skills namely active listening, passive listening, acknowledge response and encouragement. Nodding occurs during the passive listening which indicates that the pharmacist is listening it is called acknowledge

response. whereas the passive response means the patient listens to the Pharmacist attentively without interrupting, and active listening means it involves 2 ways interactions between the patient and the pharmacist which should be continued always after the passive listening [12].

1) COMMUNICATE VERBALLY:

The pharmacist needs to communicate with the patient verbally, and should ask all the information about medication that is provided by the physician and the pharmacist should ask the questions in an open-ended manner it should be like, can you please tell me what are the medications that are prescribed, rather than asking what are the medications prescribed, so the pharmacist needs to communicate verbally [13].

2) COMMUNICATE NON VERBALLY

Other than verbal communication pharmacist needs to communicate with the patient non verbally also pharmacist needs to be aware of the facial expressions, and also head nodding and eye contact, tone of voice [14].

CONDUCT OF CLINICAL PHARMACIST IN PATIENT COUNSELING

Patient counseling plays a major role for the patient right from the simply dosing the drug to the advice of the life style changes.

Patient counseling plays a major role for the patient right from the simply dosing the drug to the advice of the life style changes. Pharmacist should make sure that patient understands the medication and uses them appropriately. The pharmacist should make sure that the direction of

the drugs should label on the prescription. Patient counselling is a best method that helps in reducing the medication adherence and also medication related problems. The pharmacist should be available to the patient any time for providing information. Most importantly good communication is very much important for the patients . communication means not only about speaking clearly but also involves the good listening and also understanding. While speaking with the patient the time of the pharmacist should be very clear and also volume should be in a proper level [15].

ATTITUDE OF PATIENT TOWARDS CLINICAL PHARMACIST:

The Clinical pharmacist faces a major problem while addressing the ethnic and racial information about the patient. Sometimes the patient are also unwilling for providing the information.some of the recent studies shows that the patient who are not willing to provide information to the pharmacist are very much comfortable for providing information to the nurse or physican[16].

EFFECT OF PATIENT COUNSELLING IN HYPERTENSION BY CLINICAL PHARMACIST:

The patients are counselled by the clinical pharmacist by provinding them the patient information leaflets (PILS). The pharmacist need to advise the patients to take medication correctly and also should inform to the patient when and what to take at right time and also the food that to be consumed also should be informed by the pharmacist to the patient and also exercises that should be done the patient regular to maintain correct blood pressure that is 140/90 and the pharmacist should take part in prescribing the adverse drug events of medication and also the possible drug drug and drug food interactions and also contraindications of such medication if the patient are suffering from any of the underlying diseases such as CHF,DM, Asthma etc [17].

EFFECT OF PATIENT COUNSELLING IN DIABETES MELLITUS BY CLINICAL PHARMACIST:

Patient counselling help to improve the medication adherence and also help in life style modification of the patients . The patient counselling should be conducted in privacy so that it will be clear to the patient . And the clinical pharmacist must focus on the adverse Drug events that mainly occur after taking the medication some of the drugs that need to be closely monitor are 1) INSULIN it should be injected at the right time and it should be injected before meals the dose should not missed the patients are always advised to Carry a sugar candy all the times if there is occurrence of hypoglycemia. Which is major side effect of insulin . Storage of insulin should be done in refrigerator at temperature of 2- 80 degrees Celsius and always insulin should be administered subcutaneous route .2) METFORMIN the

Common side effects of metformin namely include Diarrhea, anorexia, abdominal pain and gi distress , metallic taste .This drug must be taken with the meals . And also patients with renal function need to be assessed and also patients with hepatic disease may leads to lactic acidosis and also cardiac failure. The patients with renal impairment should not prescribe metformin[18].

EFFECT OPATIENT COUNSELLING BY CLINICAL PHARMACIST IN PEDIATRICS

Pediatrics these are the more important group of population who undergo majorly drug related problems due to their underdeveloped pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamic properties .The pediatric clinical pharmacist play a major role in the hospital for understanding the medication profile. The clinical pharmacist role manly is to medication errors adrs and also other medication related problems which mainly leads to morbidity and mortality. In pediatrics mainly the interaction between the clinical pharmacist and the physician leads to best outcome of the children [19].

EFFECT PATIENT COUNSELLING BY CLINICAL PHARMACIST IN GERIATRICS

Geriatric counselling is mainly focus on the older people with many complex health problems which mainly involves impairment, disability, instability, iatrogenic properties and incontinence. Most of the elderly people suffer from psychiatric problems which mainly involves Dementia, anxiety disorders and depression. And also the pathological function of the elderly people may change which leads to various problems like gastric

problems and also coronary problems . So pharmacist need to be careful while prescribing medication to the elderly people and the pharmacist need to be carefully monitor the adverse drug events and also drug interactions with food and other drugs. The elderly people with disability may feel frustrated ,so clinical pharmacist need to be very careful while handling the geriatric patients and they should provide all the information to the patients through patience[20].

CONCLUSION

Patient counselling is getting popularized in India since last 10 years,it is one of the very important way to reach the heart of public through a profession of Pharmacist in which pharmacist play a major role in guiding and taking care of patients and majorly patient counselling mainly helps in eradication of medication errors and also adverse drug events and also medication adherence. Pharmacist in the hospital play the vital role right from the prescription to the patient compliance. The proper patient counselling

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